

Name: Josh Wilbur

Language, LIC: Plains Cree, ??

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Sources:

1. Dahlstrom, Amy. *Plains Cree Morphosyntax*. Garland Publishing: New York, London, 1991;
2. Wolfart, H. Christoph. *Plains Cree: A Grammatical Study*. The American Philosophical Society: Philadelphia, 1973.
3. Russell, Kevin. "The 'Word' in two Polysynthetic Languages." in *Studies on the Phonological Word*, Hall, Kleinherz.
4. Bloomfield, L. *Sacred Stories of the Sweet Grass Cree*. F. A. Acland: Ottawa, 1930.

NOTE: of the four sources above, Russell seems by far most concerned with considering what defines phonetic word in Plains Cree.

5. Davenport, M. & S. J. Hannahs, *Introducing Phonetics and Phonology*. London, Arnold, 1998 (as quoted in T. A. Hall's *Phonologie: eine Einführung* 2000)

-a phonetic inventory (3):

vowels: *i, a, o, i:, e:, a:, o:* (long vowels often transcribed with a circumflex ^)

consonants: *p, t, k, m, n, y* (I assume this correlates to IPA [j]), *w, h* (before an obstruent, h represents preaspiration), plus *ts* and *tf* (alternates both transcribed with *c*) and *s* and *f* (alternates both transcribed with *s*).

-Phon.-ω: minimally bimoraic (content words subject to stringent bisyllabic minimum, whereas functional particles can be one heavy syllable) (3)

-Stress: antepenultimate (but penultimate if bisyllabic, ultimate if monosyllabic) (3)

-optional ω-final devoicing: word final V in Cree is *optionally* devoiced toward the end of V (indicated by Bloomfield transcription with word-final *h*) (3)

anima ~ animah (‘that one’)

-(3): NO devoicing between verb stem and suffix, between halves of a compound (p. 209)

-but contrary (2): “the final vowels of compound members are subject to the same gradual devoicing as those of simple words” (p. 76)

-two Vs adjacent across word boundary, optional coalescence or deletion of first V with compensatory lengthening of second V (external sandhi) (3)

e:kwani anima --> e:kwana:anima

and that:one

-Final short V subject to apocope (unless stem is monosyllabic; sometimes not if stem vowel is long) (2, p. 82):

/si:si:p-a/ --> [si:si:p] (‘duck’ proximate sg. animate)

but

/nisk-a/ --> [niska] (‘goose’)

-Post-C final /w/ dropped (2):

/e:-apiyahkw/ --> [e:-apiyahk] (‘when we were sitting’)

-Lots of fusion between morpheme boundaries!

replacement rules for combining morphemes; see (2):

but only one rule given with effects at ω-level: /w/ --> Ø / _#, _-/w/

Diminutives: there is usually palatalization of all /t/ (which includes [t] and [θ]) in a word when containing a diminutive suffix *-es, -esis* (2)

nite:m --> nice:misis

‘my horse’ ‘my little horse’

aθemw- --> acimosis

‘dog’ ‘little dog’

Compounds:

(2, p. 75): “Compounds differ from unit words and resemble phrases in that the sandhi between compound members is of the external type [external sandhi is optional]; that is, even though not all compound members actually occur separately as free forms, they are nevertheless treated like words phonologically.” This indicates that P-ω show external sandhi.

ex (note the loss of /i/ and lengthening of /a/):

isi + atoske:w --> isa:toske:w

'thus' 'he works' 'thus he works'

(2, p. 76,77):

-Nominal compounds consist of a noun or an initial particle and a noun: N/part + N

-Verbal compounds consist of preverb particle(s) and a verb stem: Part(s) + V-stem

So, these elements of a compound are implicitly considered P- ω by Wolfart, which is what Russell then argues for (concerning verbal compounds) in his article (3).

"Initial vowels have an on-glide of *h* under stress, especially in interjections; *hay hay*! "splendid!" (4, p.2)

-Based solely on my analyses of the examples from (2):

In the surface structure, two vowels never occur together in any context; there are no stems with VV and all the fusion rules make it impossible for VV to occur across any morpheme boundaries (including those between words).

-the following phonological rule (5, as quoted in T. A. Hall's *Phonologie: eine Einführung* 2000, p. 42) could potentially be used as a test for P- ω -hood if it is indeed only a word-internal process (unfortunately I haven't been able to find the original source for this information):

/p t k/ --> [b d g] / V_V

examples from *Phonologie: eine Einführung*:

/asapa:p/ --> [asaba:p] 'thread'

/takosin/ --> [tagosin] 'he's arriving'

/nisita/ --> [nisida] 'my feet'

(I assume these examples are considered P- ω , although I haven't been able to get a hold of the original source to check on this. For whatever its worth, the English-Cree dictionary was not helpful at all in determining morpheme boundaries, but did have the following entries (apparently based on the phonological representations): *asapap* = thread, *takosin* = s/he is arriving, *misita* = feet, *misit* = foot; it would be interesting for example to find out what the actual pronunciation of *misit* would be with another P- ω after it, but I don't know how to find this out.)